

MATURITY-ONSET DIABETES OF THE YOUNG: ETIOLOGY AND PATHOGENESIS

Sh. Sh. Mukhtarova¹, M. A. Ablakimova², D. S. Tojiddinova³, A. Kh. Allaberdieva⁴
Tashkent State Medical University^{1,2,3,4}

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20067263>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the causes and mechanisms of development of maturity-onset diabetes of the young. The role of hereditary factors, insulin resistance, β -cell dysfunction, and environmental influences in the formation of the disease is highlighted. It is also noted that metabolic disorders, disruption of carbohydrate metabolism, and hormonal changes play an important role in the pathogenesis of the disease.*

The results of the study show that the early development of diabetes in young people increases the risk of later complications, and timely detection of this condition, as well as treatment based on an individual approach, is considered important. In this regard, improving early diagnosis and preventive measures for this disease is an urgent task.

Keywords: *maturity-Onset Diabetes of the Young - MODY, heredity, MODY 1, HNF4A mutation, MODY 2, GCK mutation, MODY 3, HNF1A mutation.*

Introduction

Maturity-Onset Diabetes of the Young - MODY - is a type of diabetes mellitus characterized by impaired insulin secretion in the beta cells of the pancreas and has a monogenic, that is, single-gene mutation, and hereditary nature. The most common forms of diabetes mellitus include autoimmune type 1 diabetes and polygenic type 2 diabetes, which develops under the influence of genetics and environmental factors. At present, there are more than two forms of diabetes, and sometimes hybrid forms are also encountered.

MODY is a type of monogenic diabetes described as a mild and asymptomatic form of diabetes observed in children, adolescents, and young adults, first identified in non-obese children. Improvement in blood glucose levels was observed during treatment with sulfonylureas. With the expansion of genetic technologies, many genes associated with MODY have been studied. This study reviews the presentation, evaluation, and management of MODY and emphasizes the role of a professional team-based approach in patient treatment.

In 1974, based on the studies conducted by Tattersall and Fajans, the term “Maturity-Onset Diabetes of the Young” - MODY - was introduced [1]. MODY is the most common form of monogenic diabetes and is inherited in an autosomal dominant manner. Patients with this type of diabetes may sometimes be misdiagnosed as having type 1 diabetes or type 2 diabetes. It usually manifests before the age of 25. This form of diabetes is non-ketotic, and pancreatic autoantibodies are not detected in patients. It occurs due to beta-cell dysfunction.

In identifying this syndrome, it is important to know whom to examine. Since it is inherited in an autosomal dominant manner, the condition may also occur in the patient’s family members. In addition, certain genetic subtypes respond differently to treatment, have different levels of complications, and some may be associated with other pancreatic or extra-pancreatic abnormalities involving the kidneys, liver, intestines, and other organs [2]. There are six commonly recognized subtypes.

Materials and Methods

This study is based on a theoretical and analytical review of scientific literature on maturity-onset diabetes of the young. The materials of the study include published clinical, genetic, endocrinological, and molecular-biological studies devoted to MODY, its etiology, epidemiology, pathophysiology, clinical presentation, diagnosis, and treatment. The methods used in the study include literature analysis, comparative analysis of MODY subtypes, generalization of scientific data, and clinical interpretation of diagnostic and therapeutic approaches.

Results and Discussion

Etiology

MODY arises due to defects in the development of pancreatic islets, which leads to impaired insulin secretion. It is usually inherited in an autosomal dominant manner, and patients typically have heterozygous mutations. Penetrance and expressivity may vary greatly, even among family members, and phenotypically depend on the gene involved [3]. MODY genes affect insulin secretion through impaired insulin sensitivity, glucose metabolism in beta cells, or activation of adenosine triphosphate-dependent potassium channels [4].

Epidemiology

MODY accounts for less than 5.0% of all patients with diabetes. At present, it is estimated that 6.5% of children with antibody-negative diabetes have a MODY form [5,6]. The disease usually begins between the ages of 10 and 40. Patients with MODY have genotypic features of both type 1 and type 2 diabetes and are often misdiagnosed as having type 1 diabetes or type 2 diabetes. Therefore, as the number of MODY diagnoses increases, its prevalence may prove to be higher.

Although MODY has mainly been described in Caucasian populations, it has also been reported by Jialal among other ethnic groups, such as Asian Indians in South Africa [7].

Pathophysiology

Although type 1 diabetes and type 2 diabetes are polygenic, MODY occurs due to a mutation in a single gene that leads to a defect in insulin secretion by beta cells in response to glucose stimulation. Most genetic forms of MODY have autosomal dominant inheritance. However, less commonly, autosomal recessive forms may also exist and may cause diabetes in newborns.

Initially, the types of MODY were described numerically as MODY 1–6. However, they are now classified according to their genetic defects.

At present, at least 14 different MODY mutations are known. These include: **GCK, HNF1A, HNF4A, HNF1B, INS, NEURO1, PDX1, PAX4, ABCC8, KCNJ11, KLF11, CEL, BLK, and APPL1**. Different genes vary in terms of age of onset, response to treatment, and the presence of extra-pancreatic manifestations.

The most common gene mutations are as follows: mutation in the hepatocyte nuclear factor 1 alpha gene - HNF1A - accounts for 30% to 60% of MODY cases. Mutation in the hepatocyte nuclear factor 4 alpha gene - HNF4A - accounts for 5% to 10% of MODY cases. Mutations in the glucokinase gene - GCK - account for 30% to 60% of MODY cases. Mutation in the hepatocyte nuclear factor 1 beta gene - HNF1B - accounts for less than 5% of MODY cases. The distribution of MODY genes varies from country to country.

MODY 3: HNF1A Mutation

In MODY 3, mutation in the HNF1A gene affects key stages of glucose transport and metabolism in pancreatic beta cells, as well as mitochondrial metabolism. HNF1A is found in the

liver, kidneys, and intestines, as well as in pancreatic tissue. Progressive dysfunction of beta cells is present. In these patients, the renal threshold for glucosuria is reduced.

The diagnosis of HNF1A-related MODY is usually made between the ages of 21 and 26. The genetic defect has high penetrance: 63% of carriers develop diabetes by the age of 25, 79% by the age of 35, and 96% by the age of 35 [8,9].

HNF1A-related MODY is highly sensitive to sulfonylureas and meglitinides, although beta cells do not respond well to hyperglycemia by producing and releasing insulin [10]. The mechanism of action involves the binding of the drug to sulfonylurea receptors located on the beta-cell membranes. This triggers calcium influx, which leads to the fusion of vesicles containing stored insulin [11]. The use of sulfonylurea drugs can often delay the need for insulin replacement for many years.

MODY 2: GCK Mutation

Glucokinase is an enzyme that enables pancreatic beta cells and hepatocytes to respond to glucose levels. In GCK gene mutation, or MODY 2, the glucose threshold for insulin secretion is reset, leading to elevated fasting glucose levels. An oral glucose tolerance test shows only a slight increase in glucose concentration.

Patients with GCK mutation usually demonstrate mild and non-progressive hyperglycemia, which is typically asymptomatic. In these patients, HbA1c is usually less than 8%, and the risk of microvascular, and possibly macrovascular, complications is low [8,12].

MODY 1: HNF4A Mutation

MODY 1, caused by HNF4A mutation, is less common than MODY caused by GCK mutation. Its presentation is similar to HNF1A-related MODY. It should be considered when a patient has features similar to HNF4A mutation but genetic testing is negative.

Patients with HNF4A mutation may have reduced HDL-C levels and therefore may resemble patients with type 2 diabetes more closely. In addition, these patients often have higher birth weight and a higher rate of macrosomia. They may also present with transient neonatal hypoglycemia [9]. HNF4A should be suspected in patients with a strong family history of diabetes mellitus and neonatal hypoglycemia.

Sulfonylureas work well in the treatment of hyperglycemia [13]. Both HNF1A and HNF4A are genes that regulate the expression of many genes encoding serum proteins, such as blood coagulation factors and apolipoproteins [14].

HNF1B: MODY 5

HNF1B-related MODY accounts for less than 5% of cases. It is associated with a wide variety of manifestations. Patients may have abnormalities such as renal cysts, dysplasia, malformations of the urinary tract, or hypoplastic glomerulocystic kidney disease. HNF1B MODY is sometimes referred to as RCAD - renal cysts and diabetes syndrome.

Renal function may progressively decline independently of diabetic nephropathy [15]. Patients with HNF1B usually do not respond to oral medications and require insulin treatment.

PDX1: MODY 4

A defect in IPF1, insulin gene promoter factor 1, causes another form of MODY. PDX1 is a homeobox-containing transcription factor that affects pancreatic development and the expression of the insulin gene.

NEUROD1: MODY 6

NEUROD1 is a mutation in a basic helix-loop-helix transcription factor that affects the development of the pancreas and neurons. Most patients require insulin treatment [16].

ABCC8: MODY 12 and KCNJ11: MODY 13

Mutations in ABCC8 and KCNJ11 are associated with a range of conditions, such as neonatal diabetes [9]. Neonatal diabetes may be permanent or transient; in the latter case, it often recurs later in life. Neonatal diabetes is associated with mutations in potassium-ATP channel genes or mutations in the insulin gene [5].

In addition, these mutations are associated with neonatal hypoglycemia due to increased insulin levels. This is usually transient, but the patient may develop diabetes later in life. In such cases, it may be very important to monitor fetal growth during pregnancy and blood glucose levels in newborns. Patients with diabetes usually respond well to sulfonylurea drugs.

History and Physical Presentation

The initial history should include a detailed personal medical history. The diagnosis of MODY diabetes usually occurs during adolescence or early adulthood. Therefore, details related to the diagnosis of diabetes are very important. Birth history, if available, may also provide useful information.

In patients with HNF1B, or MODY 5, intrauterine growth restriction - IUGR - may be observed together with certain congenital anomalies, such as renal and urinary tract abnormalities, as well as pancreatic hypoplasia. In those with the HNF4A subtype, or MODY 1, birth weight is usually more than 800 grams above normal, and transient neonatal hyperinsulinemic hypoglycemia may also be observed. Patients with GCK, or MODY 2, may have a history of mild fasting hyperglycemia from birth. Some patients with HNF1A, or MODY 3, may have transient neonatal hyperinsulinemic hypoglycemia [17].

The personal medical history should include a complete review of systems and questions about known medical problems related to other organ systems, because some forms of MODY may be associated with extra-beta-cell manifestations, such as involvement of the kidneys, liver, genitourinary system, exocrine pancreas, or intestines.

Physical examination does not provide any specific information that helps diagnose MODY or a particular subtype. Patients with MODY may have normal body weight or may be lean, although obesity may also be present in these patients [17]. In general, physical examination should include the basic assessments performed for any patient with diabetes, because some forms of MODY cause complications. Therefore, in addition to urinary microalbumin and lipid panel tests, patients should be screened for retinopathy and neuropathy.

Treatment

The optimal treatment method for diabetes associated with MODY varies depending on the gene mutation. Therefore, knowing the genetic subtype is important for understanding treatment and prognosis in these patients.

In MODY 2, or GCK mutation, patients have elevated fasting blood glucose levels, but usually do not develop postprandial hyperglycemia, because insulin secretion in response to increased glucose levels is sufficient. These patients usually require only lifestyle and dietary changes [22].

For MODY 3, or HNF1A mutation, and MODY 1, or HNF4A mutation, patients can usually initially be managed only through dietary modification. These patients develop postprandial hyperglycemia after carbohydrate-rich meals [23]. Over time, they may experience deterioration of beta-cell function and require treatment. These patients tend to respond well to sulfonylureas.

An alternative treatment option is a glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonist - GLP-1RA. A randomized controlled trial comparing GLP-1RA with glimepiride in the treatment of MODY 3 patients showed that these drugs are similar in lowering blood glucose, although glimepiride had a slightly stronger glucose-lowering effect, but with an increased risk of hypoglycemia [24].

Patients with MODY 5, or HNF1B mutation, usually do not respond well to sulfonylurea drugs. This may be partly explained by the simultaneous presence of pancreatic hypoplasia, in addition to the degree of hepatic insulin resistance [25].

Thus, these patients usually require insulin to control hyperglycemia. This subgroup of MODY patients is characterized by a tendency toward microvascular complications. In particular, their renal function should be carefully monitored, because most of these patients develop renal dysfunction by the age of 45 and may progress to end-stage renal disease [26]. In general, because the number of cases is small and these subtypes are rare, guidelines are not available for many of the subtypes.

Treatment of MODY in Young People

In many countries, metformin and insulin are approved for use in young people. Some countries have approved the use of sulfonylurea drugs in adolescent populations. Otherwise, no other class of oral antidiabetic agents is approved for those under the age of 18 [27].

Treatment During Pregnancy

As noted above, GCK MODY usually does not require treatment outside pregnancy. Determining which GCK MODY patients need treatment depends on the fetal genotype. This is not determined genetically but is assessed by fetal abdominal circumference measured during the second trimester.

If this value exceeds 75%, it indicates that the fetus does not have the GCK mutation; therefore, these mothers should be treated with insulin during pregnancy to prevent macrosomia [28]. If the fetal abdominal circumference is less than 75%, this means that the fetus does not carry the gene, because it has the same elevated glucose level as the mother, and therefore maternal hyperglycemia is perceived as normal by the fetus. As a result, growth remains normal, insulin treatment is not indicated for the mother, and such treatment may even lead to growth restriction [28].

Conclusion

MODY is a distinct and clinically important subtype of diabetes mellitus, which requires a differential approach to diagnosis and treatment because of its specific genetic basis, pathophysiological mechanisms, and variable clinical presentation. Understanding its etiology and classification is important for distinguishing MODY from the common forms of diabetes mellitus, particularly type 1 and type 2 diabetes, and for establishing an accurate diagnosis at the early stages of the disease.

The comprehensive use of clinical assessment, biochemical tests, analysis of family history, and molecular-genetic confirmation methods plays an important role as the basis of effective diagnosis. Treatment tactics should be selected individually, based on the patient's individual characteristics and the specific subtype of MODY, and may include lifestyle modification, oral hypoglycemic drugs, or insulin therapy when necessary.

In addition, timely identification of MODY has great practical importance not only for effective management of the patient's condition but also for screening family members and providing genetic counseling, taking into account the hereditary nature of the disease. Further

scientific research on genotype–phenotype relationships and targeted treatment strategies will help increase the accuracy of MODY diagnosis and improve long-term clinical outcomes.

REFERENCES

1. Tattersall, R. B. (1974). Mild familial diabetes with dominant inheritance. *QJM: An International Journal of Medicine*, 43(170), 339–357.
2. Nyunt, O., et al. (2009). An overview of MODY: Maturity-onset diabetes of the young. *Clinical Biochemist Reviews*, 30(2), 67–74.
3. Yahaya, T. O., & Ufuoma, S. B. (2020). Genetics and pathophysiology of MODY: A review of current trends. *Oman Medical Journal*, 35(3), e126.
4. Ashcroft, F. M. (2005). ATP-sensitive potassium channelopathies: Focus on insulin secretion. *Journal of Clinical Investigation*, 115(8), 2047–2058.
5. Yang, Y., & Chan, L. (2016). Monogenic diabetes: What it teaches us about type 1 and type 2 diabetes. *Endocrine Reviews*, 37(3), 190–222.
6. Owen, K. R. (2018). Monogenic diabetes in adults: What are the new developments? *Current Opinion in Genetics & Development*, 50, 103–110.
7. Jialal, I., et al. (1986). The spectrum of non-insulin-dependent diabetes in the young. *Diabetes Research*, 3(9), 479–481.
8. Wędrychowicz, A., et al. (2017). Phenotypic heterogeneity in patients with GCK-MODY. *Journal of Clinical Research in Pediatric Endocrinology*, 9(3), 246–252.
9. Gardner, D. S., & Tai, E. S. (2012). Clinical features and treatment options for MODY. *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity*, 5, 101–108.
10. Kim, S. H. (2015). Maturity-onset diabetes of the young: What do clinicians need to know? *Diabetes & Metabolism Journal*, 39(6), 468–477.
11. Brunerova, L., et al. (2018). Use of oral antidiabetic drugs in the treatment of MODY. *Diabetes/Metabolism Research and Reviews*, 34(1).
12. Bansal, V., et al. (2017). Spectrum of mutations in monogenic diabetes genes. *BMC Medicine*, 15(1), 213.
13. Horikawa, Y. (2018). Maturity-onset diabetes of the young as a model for elucidating the multifactorial origin of type 2 diabetes. *Journal of Diabetes Investigation*, 9(4), 704–712.
14. Fajans, S. S., & Bell, G. I. (2011). MODY: History, genetics, pathophysiology, and clinical decision making. *Diabetes Care*, 34(8), 1878–1884.
15. Mikuscheva, A., et al. (2017). A 21-year-old pregnant woman with MODY-5 diabetes. *Case Reports in Obstetrics and Gynecology*.
16. Rubio-Cabezas, O., et al. (2010). Neonatal diabetes and neurological impairment caused by homozygous mutations in the NEUROD1 gene. *Diabetes*, 59(9), 2326–2331.
17. Naylor, R., et al. (2018). Maturity-onset diabetes of the young overview. *GeneReviews*.
18. Ellard, S., et al. (2008). Best practice guidelines for the molecular genetic diagnosis of MODY. *Diabetologia*, 51(4), 546–553.
19. Steele, A. M., et al. (2013). Use of HbA1c in detecting hyperglycemia caused by GCK mutations. *PLOS ONE*, 8(6), e65326.
20. McDonald, T. J., et al. (2011). High-sensitivity C-reactive protein discriminates HNF1A-MODY from other forms of diabetes. *Diabetes Care*, 34(8), 1860–1862.
21. Besser, R. E., et al. (2011). Urinary C-peptide/creatinine ratio as a non-invasive method in type 1 diabetes. *Diabetes Care*, 34(3), 607–609.

22. Urakami, T. (2019). Maturity-onset diabetes of the young: Current perspectives on diagnosis and treatment. *Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome and Obesity*, 12, 1047–1056.
23. Stride, A., et al. (2002). The genetic abnormality in the beta cell determines the response to an oral glucose load. *Diabetologia*, 45(3), 427–435.
24. Østoft, S., et al. (2014). Effect of a GLP-1 receptor agonist in patients with MODY. *Diabetes Care*, 37(7), 1797–1805.
25. Murphy, R., et al. (2008). Clinical implications of a molecular genetic classification of monogenic beta-cell diabetes. *Nature Clinical Practice Endocrinology & Metabolism*, 4(4), 200–213.
26. Bingham, C., et al. (2001). Mutations in the hepatocyte nuclear factor-1 β gene are associated with familial hypoplastic glomerulocystic kidney disease. *American Journal of Human Genetics*, 68(1), 219–224.
27. Zeitler, P., et al. (2018). ISPAD clinical practice consensus guidelines: Type 2 diabetes mellitus in youth. *Pediatric Diabetes*, 19(Suppl. 27), 28–46.
28. Dickens, L. T., et al. (2019). Pregnancy and delivery outcomes in women with GCK-MODY. *Acta Diabetologica*, 56(4), 405–411.